

ability and produce many grains per panicle (Table 1). Both varieties have grain type similar to that of Molagolukulu, which is locally preferred. Grains are short and bold with white, translucent kernels and have excellent cooking and keeping qualities. Seed dormancy also is desirable. Both the varieties perform well, even if 60-d-old seedlings are planted late in wet season. NLR9672 is moderately resistant to B1 and bacterial blight, and NLR9674 is B1 resistant.

In five yield trials from 1970 to 1974 (Aug-Sep to Jan), NLR9672 followed by NLR9674 yielded significantly higher than Bulk H/9. In 1975 minikit trials at 20 sites in Nellore. NLR9672 yielded an average 17% and NLR9674 10% higher than Bulk H/9 (Table 2).

NLR9672 is grown on 250,000 ha and NLR9674 is on 200,000 ha in Nellore

Table 1. Agronomic traits of NLR9672 and NLR9674 at Nellore, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	1,000-grain wt (g)
NLR9672	160	100	248	339	23.5
NLR9674	170	104	269	326	22.5
BulkH/9	180	150	198	192	22.0

Table 2. Grain yields of NLR9672 and NLR9674 at Nellore, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)						1975 minikit trial ^a
	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	Mean	
NLR9672	5.4	5.7	6.1	3.8	4.4	5.1	4.0
NLR9674	5.2	5.7	5.9	3.5	4.1	4.9	3.7
BulkH/9	3.8	5.4	5.3	3.1	3.3	4.2	3.3
CD P = 0.05	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.5		

^a Mean of 20 locations.

and Prakasam and parts of Guntur, Cuddapah, and Chittoor. *J*

New varieties derived from BG96-2

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BG90-2 was developed in Sri Lanka. Introduced in China in 1976, it was released in Nanjing as a midseason variety in 1979 because it has excellent

morphoagronomic characters and high resistance to bacterial blight (RH). Its growth duration exceeds 150 d. however, which makes it difficult to grow after wheat. Several promising varieties or lines have been developed from BG90-2.

B-xuan 1 and B-fu 1 were selected from BG90-2 by the Jiangpu County Institute of Agricultural Sciences in 1979; 910 and Yang-dao 1 were developed by the Yangzhou District Institute of Agricultural Sciences,

Yangzhou. Jungsu Province, in 1980. B-xuan 1, 910, and Yang-dao 1 were derived from BG90-2 as pureline selections, but B-fu 1 was developed by irradiating BG90-2 seeds with Co⁶⁰ gamma rays. The new varieties and lines have shorter growth duration than BG90-2 and good characters (see table). They have been widely planted in Honan, Hubei, Anhui, and Jiangsu Provinces. By 1984 they had covered 400,000ha. *J*

Characteristics of varieties derived from BG90-2, Nanjing, China.

Variety	Height (cm)	Seeding to full heading (d)	Growth duration (d)	Panicle length (m)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Fertile grains/panicle (no.)	Sterility (%)	1,000-seed wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Reaction ^a to BB
B-xuan 1	107	102	136	28	131	102	22	30	8.8	R
910	100	103	137	28	136	100	27	29	8.6	R
Yang-dao 1	91	97	129	24	132	116	13	25	7.7	S
B-fu 1	106	95	126	26	111	98	12	36	7.6	R
BG90-2 (parent)	113	115	154	26	161	128	20	27	8.2	R

^a R = resistant, S = susceptible.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

HKR120, a promising new rice

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HKR120 is a promising, medium-duration (140-145 d) semidwarf

developed from Ptb 33/4*IR3403-267-1 at IRRI. Tested in the 1981 International Rice Observational Nursery, it showed good phenotypic acceptability. Under evaluation at HAURRS in 1982-84, it yielded more and had better tillering capacity than the checks PR106 and Jaya. It has yield

stability (see table) because it is resistant to bacterial blight (BB) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), which are major pests in Haryana. Its grains are long, slender, translucent, and have no white belly. Quality is as good as that of PR106. ✍

Performance of HKR120 in Haryana, India.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha) 1982-84	Duration (d)	Panicles/m ²	Milling (%)	Length: Width	Kernel elongation (mm)	Cooking quality	BB ^a (0-9 scale)	WBPH ^b (0-5 scale)	Rating ^c
HKR120	6.5	146	296	67	3.43	1.98	Good	3	0.73	R
PR106	6.1	148	313	67	3.25	1.98	Good	7	4.0	S
Jaya	6.0	147	298	71	2.86	1.76	Fair	7	4.5	S
CD at 5%	0.5	0.7	0.3							
CV%	5.4	7.5	3.9							

^a Based on the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^b Based on Kalode et al 1975. ^c R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Disease-resistant IRRI varieties in Tamil Nadu

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Between 1982 and 1984, blast (B1) and tungro virus (RTV) caused serious yield losses in Tamil Nadu. Commonly grown TKM9 and IR50 were susceptible to B1 and ADT31, ADT36, TKM9, and IR20, to RTV. We evaluated 37 IRRI rices for disease resistance at TNRRI in 1984-85 kuruvai (Jun planted) and thaladi (Sep planted).

For RTV screening in the glasshouse, 1 viruliferous green leafhopper that had fed for 4 d on RTV-infected plants was placed on each 10-d-old seedling for 2 d. For B1 screening in the greenhouse, 15-d-old seedlings were spray-inoculated with a conidial suspension (20,000 cells/ml) of the B1 fungus and kept in polythene tents in high humidity for 24 h before and after spraying. The varieties were also field-screened under natural conditions with 100 kg applied N/ha. Disease incidence was scored by

Disease resistance of IRRI varieties in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Disease infection								
	RTV(%)		Leaf Bl		Neck				
	Glasshouse	Field	Greenhouse (0-9)	Field (%)	B1 (%)	ShR (%)	BS (0-9)	BLB (0-9)	G1D (%)
IR9179-209-2-2-2-3	8	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0
IR13423-10-2-3	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	1	Stray
IR13429-299-2-1-3-1 (IR60)	4	0	0	0	0	3	3	1	0
IR1 7494-32-1-1-3-2	16	8	0	0	1	3	1	5	
IR18349-53-1-3-1-3	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	5	
IR24632-34-2	14	0	0	0	5	3	3	10	
IR31802-48-2-2-2	8	0	0	0	3	3	1	10	
IR32307-10-2-1-1	10	0	0	0	1	3	3	0	
IR32385-37-3-3-3	24	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	
IR32429-47-3-2	19	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	
IR32429-68-3-3-3	7	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	
IR13423-17-1-2-1	0	0	5	4	0	1	1	5	
IR13927-40-2-3-3-3-3	0	0	3	1	0	3	3	1	0
IR28143-66-3-3-2	0	0	5	37	0	1	3	1	5
IR31851-63-1-2-3-2	0	0	7	60	0	0	3	1	2
IR31868-64-2-3-3-3	0	0	5	3	0	3	3	0	9
IR29725-3-1-3-2	0	0	3	5	1	3	3	3	0
IR54	18	5.9	0	0	0	3	3	1	5
IR58	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	Stray	0
IR50	0	0	7	50	40	5	5	3	5
Co33	62	57.6	7	62	58	7	5	9	10
TKM9	65	60.0	7	53	45	5	5	3	5
ADT36	70	58.5	3	6	0	5	3	5	5
IR20	48	45.0	3	4	0	3	3	3	2

the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale (see table).

Only RTV was present in kuruvai. In thaladi, RTV, B1, sheath rot (ShR),

brown spot (BS), bacterial leaf blight (BLB), and grain discoloration (G1D) were common. Evaluation of these selections will continue in 1985. ✍